

Solvent Effects on Acid-Base Equilibria

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Equilibrium constants for acidbase equilibria of the type

have been determined by an indicator method in a few solvents and the effect of solvent on such equilibria is discussed. It has been shown that specific solute-solvent interactions as exemplified by the free energies of transfer of the various species involved in the equilibria must also be considered in addition to the electrostatic effects in understanding such equilibria.

Solvent effects on isoelectric equilibria of the type

where R_1 and R_2 may be an aliphatic or an aromatic group and a substituted derivative of them by E.M.F. and indicator methods have received considerable attention¹ in recent years. However, very little systematic work and analysis of such equilibria involving aliphatic or aromatic bases is available and the present investigation deals with such studies by an indicator method in a few solvents.

EXPERIMENTAL

(a) *Solvents, indicators and bases*: *n*-propanol, 20% (W/W) dioxan-water, 30% and 50% (W/W) methanol-water were used as solvents. The organic solvents which were B.D.H. (L.R. grade) were purified according to standard methods before use. 2,4-dinitrophenol and *p*-nitrophenols employed as the indicators were recrystallised from suitable solvents and their melting points agreed with literature values. All the aromatic amines, used as bases, were purified by standard methods and their purity was checked by a non-aqueous titration in glacial acetic acid according to the method of Palit *et al.*².

(b) *Procedure*: Initially, the following equilibrium given by

was studied using one of the nitrophenols by spectrophotometric method. Determination of the same equilibrium replacing aniline by a substituted aniline and taking the ratio of the two equilibrium constants gave another equilibrium constant K_r , for a reaction of the type

where

$$K_r = \frac{[\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{NH}_3^+][\text{RC}_6\text{H}_4\text{NH}_2]}{[\text{RC}_6\text{H}_4\text{NH}_3^+][\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{NH}_2]}$$

The general experimental procedure adopted in the indicator measurements which were done at 30° was similar to that employed by us earlier³ with some modifications. Usually in a given set of experiments the concentration of the base was varied while the indicator concentration was kept constant such that the optical densities of the experimental solution lies in the region 0.3 to 0.8. While the indicator concentration in the experimental solution was about $10^{-5}M$, the concentration of the base was maintained in the region of $10^{-2}M$ when using *p*-nitrophenol as indicator and at about $10^{-4}M$ when using 2,4-dinitrophenol as the indicator. Further details are given elsewhere⁴. The equilibrium constant of the reaction (2) was calculated from

$$K = \frac{\alpha^2 C}{(1-\alpha)(b-\alpha C)} \quad \dots (4)$$

where b and C are the stoichiometric concentrations of the base and indicator respectively and α is the degree of dissociation of the indicator given by

$$\alpha = \frac{D - D_{HA}}{D_{A^-} - D_{HA}} \quad \dots (5)$$

D , D_{HA} and D_A represent the optical densities of the experimental solution, the molecular and the ionised forms of the indicator respectively at the wavelength of measurement.

Equation (5) reduces to $\alpha = \frac{D}{D_{A^-}}$ for both the indicators as D_{HA} was found to be negligible since the measurements were carried out near the wavelength of maximum absorption of their ionic forms (at 390 nm for 2,4-DNP; at 406 nm for P.N.P.).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The ratio $K_{(aniline)}/K_{(sub-aniline)} = K_r$ was calculated for all the bases and the $\log K_r$ obtained in different media from this work are recorded along with the data available from literature in Table 1. They are also plotted in Fig. 1. The data show that K_r varies systematically with the dielectric constant of the medium despite the similar chemical nature of the species involved in reaction (3). Applying the Wynne Jones equation⁷ for the effect of dielectric constant on such equilibria and simplifying for reaction (3) assuming that one of the solvents is a hypothetical medium of infinite dielectric constant we get

$$\log K_r = \log K^{\infty}_r - \frac{e^2 N}{4.606 RT D} \left(\frac{1}{r_{A_2}} - \frac{1}{r_{A_1}} \right) \quad \dots (6)$$

In this equation, K^{∞}_r represents the value of K_r in the hypothetical medium of infinite dielectric constant, e is the electronic charge and r_{A_1} and r_{A_2} are the radii of the substituted and unsubstituted anilinium ions respectively. A plot of $\log K_r$ against $1/D$, in accordance with this equation, is linear for all the bases in solvents of similar chemical nature such as alcohols and their aqueous mixtures upto a dielectric constant of about 25, as seen from fig. 1.

The results show that, although the changes in K_r can be qualitatively accounted using equation (6), this alone cannot explain the observed results. The observed difference of $\log K_r$ for *p*-nitroanilinium ion between water and methanol is about -0.90 and equation

TABLE 1

Equilibrium constants log₁₀ K_r

Substituent in aniline	log K _r of reaction (3) in							
	H ₂ O ^{a,c}	20% (W/W) Dioxan-H ₂ O ^{b,c}	30% (W/W) CH ₃ OH-H ₂ O ^{b,c}	50% (W/W) CH ₃ OH-H ₂ O ^{b,c}	CH ₃ OH ^{a,c}	C ₂ H ₅ OH ^{a,c}	n-C ₃ H ₇ OH ^{a,b}	CH ₃ COCH ₃
o-CH ₃	+0.20	+0.19	+0.20	+0.15	+0.10	+0.10	-0.11	—
m-CH ₃	-0.09	-0.14	—	—	-0.19	-0.29	-0.87	-0.15
p-CH ₃	-0.49	-0.30	-0.50	-0.53	-0.54	-0.57	-1.25	—
N-methyl	-0.24	—	-0.18	-0.05	—	—	-0.16	—
N,N-dimethyl	-0.49	-0.26	-0.44	-0.20	—	—	—	—
o-NO ₂	+4.90	+4.78	—	—	+5.70	+6.50	—	—
m-NO ₂	+2.14	—	+2.30	+2.33	—	—	—	—
p-NO ₂	+3.60	+3.90	+3.72	+4.07	+4.50	+5.20	—	+7.21
o-Cl	+1.95	—	+2.06	+2.24	+2.40	+2.50	—	—

(a) Ref (1), (b) this work. (c) Ref. (6).

(6) requires a large difference (of about 10 Å) in the radii of anilinium and *p*-nitroanilinium ions to explain this result. Similar conclusions emerge when the large deviation of log *K_r* for this ion in acetone is examined. In particular, large differences in log *K_r* are observed

 Fig. 1. Plot of log *K_r* against 1/*D*

in dipolar aprotic solvents. The high values of log *K_r* for *p*-nitroanilinium ion in acetone and *o*-chloroanilinium ion in formamide⁸ as compared to water are most probably due to the fact that these solvents are poor hydrogen bond donors⁹. The plots for toluidinium

and N-substituted anilinium ions are, however, in better agreement with Wynne Jones equation. Expressing the ratio of K_r between water and the solvent "S" as

$$\frac{K_r(W)}{K_r(S)} = \frac{f^\circ(C_6H_5NH_3^+) \times f^\circ(RC_6H_4NH_2)}{f^\circ(RC_6H_4NH_3^+) \times f^\circ(C_6H_5NH_2)} \quad \dots \quad ()$$

where the f° terms represent the 'primary medium effects' of the various species, it is seen that this ratio is considerably affected by the medium effects of the neutral molecules on the assumption¹⁰ that the medium effects of the charged species cancel each other approximately. The importance of the medium effects of the neutral molecules in such equilibria has recently¹¹ been emphasized. However, a complete understanding of the solvent effects on acid-base equilibria in terms of equation (7) must await the development of reliable methods¹² of evaluation of the medium effects of the various species involved in the equilibria.

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